

Table 1. Rice with resistance to blast and brown spot diseases, Mandya, India.

Pedigree	
TR20/Co 29	IET 8159
Ratna Mutant	Acham/IR20
IET6080	Ar 10-169 Mutant
Hema/CR57/Vikram/Shakti/ORSTR952	CR151-79/CR1014
CR151/CR1014	Tellahamsa/W12708
IET6288	WGL 16085/Kakatiya
IET6314	Imp. Sona/Pak. Basmati
Cul-240/IR20	IET6314/Co 2
Lalnakanda/IR30	IR32/Swarnadhan
IR8/Co 25	OS4/Palguna
Dorpandy mutant	IR8/IET4141
IET7810	IET4699/Ras 370
IR2061-465-1-5-IR36	IET4699/Bas 370
Hamsraj/Saket 4	IET7748

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Table 2. Reaction of rice varieties to blast symptoms and brown spot disease at Mandya, India.

Scale ^a	Entries (no.)		
	Leaf blast	Neck blast	Brown spot
0-3	78	83	223
4-6	213	217	99
7-9	43	34	12

^aScale: 0-3 = resistant, 4-6 = moderately susceptible, 7-9 = susceptible.

IR36, a promising variety for bacterial blight-prone areas of Haryana

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IR36 is a semidwarf, medium-maturity rice variety with slender grains and bacterial blight (BB) resistance. In 1981, it was recommended by the central variety release committee for commercial cultivation in India. Varietal trials under BB stress were conducted in 1980-82 kharif at Kaul and Karnal stations.

Performance of IR36 under bacterial blight stress in Haryana, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha) during kharif				Duration (days)	Panicles/m ²	Length-breadth ratio	BB reaction ^a
	1980 (Kaul)	1981 (Karnal)	1982 (Karnal)	Mean				
IR36	5.6	7.0	5.2	5.9	135	269	2.95	3
Jaya	4.4	7.4	6.2	6.0	148	251	2.32	9
PR106	4.3	6.3	5.1	5.2	149	213	2.60	9
Palman 579	4.5	6.8	5.5	5.6	130	243	2.90	5
CD	0.85	0.56	0.89					
CV(%)	11.12	4.0	11.0					

^aBy 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

IR36 yielded better than PR106 and Palman 579 checks and was equal to Jaya (see table). IR36 had more panicles per square meter, and higher length-breadth ratio than all three checks. It matured

earlier than Jaya, which would allow good performance in wheat - rice rotation. BB infestation in 1981 and 1982 kharif was not as high as in 1980 kharif. □

Reaction of released and prerelease rice varieties to various diseases in Karnataka, India

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Blast (B1), brown spot (BS), grain discoloration (GD), and udbatta (UDb) diseases are becoming important in

Reaction of released and prerelease rice varieties to various diseases in Karnataka, India, 1982 kharif.

Variety	Disease score ^a				
	B1		BS	GD	UDb
	Leaf	Neck			
KMS8	R	R	R	R	S
IET6265	R	M	R	M	R
KMS9	R	R	R	R	R
KMS4	R	R	M	R	R
RP850	R	M	R	R	R
KMS7	R	R	R	R	R
KMP66	R	M	M	R	M

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